

Kuchai Silk: A Traditional Craft

Priya Kumari & Sankar Roy Maulik*

Department of Silpa-Sadana, Visva-Bharati (A Central University), Sriniketan, India

Abstract:

Kuchai silk is produced by tussar silkworms cultivated on the trees of Asan and Arjun. It is a part of an ancient tradition of Jharkhand, which provides livelihood in rural areas. It was started in the small village of Seraikela-Kharsawan – ‘Kuchai’ and is now spread all over Jharkhand. Currently, 30,000 people are working in the production of Kuchai silk in Jharkhand. This traditional craft is becoming a light in darkness for many people and the Jharkhand tableau in the Republic Day 2024 parade shows the production of Kuchai silk by the tribal women. Tableau plays an integral part as it displays the nation’s progress, historical significance and abundance of cultural heritage. Kuchai silk production involves long-term production processes, thus rural artisans rely on agriculture for day-to-day household management, as daily wages are insufficient.

Keywords: Jharkhand, Kuchai, Silk, Traditional, Tribes

*Corresponding Author:

Dr. Sankar Roy Maulik
Associate Professor
Department of Silpa-Sadana
Visva-Bharati (A Central University)
P.O. Sriniketan – 731 236
District: Birbhum, West Bengal
E-mail: s_r_moulik@yahoo.co.in

1. Introduction

Evolution has occurred with the change in time; people adapted different cultures and languages and migrated from one place to another. However, the ambition to create an artwork or an object for a need continues. The legacy of creating skilled work by hand from ancient times continues to inspire and influence contemporary cultures, reminding us of the timeless value of skills, commitment, and creativity in terms of functionality and elegance.

'The land of the forest'—Jharkhand is well-known for its tribal communities. Almost 32 tribal groups are in Jharkhand, representing 28% of the total state population. The primary cultures of these tribes are represented by their dance and music. The tribe or *Adivasi* community carry their cultural legacy and belief as they gather with the drums, make music and dance with their heart and soul with its rhythm, forgetting all the despair for a special occasion with all their communities [1]. The state is also known for its rich mineral resources, contributing 40% of the country's minerals. However, apart from these resources, one who visits this place will be amazed by the charm and enchanted beauty of nature, culture, temples, mountains, and waterfalls. Jharkhand was a part of Bihar before July 2000 [2]. It is situated in the northeastern part of India. Jharkhand shares its border with five states: Uttar Pradesh, Bihar, West Bengal, Chhattisgarh, and Odisha. This state is mixed with opportunities, challenges, and livelihoods through ongoing efforts to promote economic development, sustainability, and preservation of

cultures. It has three well-defined seasons, i.e., the winter (November–February), then the summer (April–June), the hottest time and the rainy season (July to September). '*Basant Ritu*', or spring season, is seen from March to April and autumn from September to October.

In the state of Jharkhand, tussar sericulture has cultural significance. It also has the potential for entrepreneurship development amongst rural people and contributes to India's tradition of silk production through innovation. The researcher addressed the impact of tussar sericulture in empowering rural entrepreneurs despite the challenges faced by the industry [3]. Jharkhand is one of the bio-diversity states in India, and most locals depend on forest resources. Forest plays an integral part in their economic, cultural and societal livelihood. The unnecessary use of plants, lack of scientific knowledge and over-grazing are some threats endangering the existing populations of important plants. Therefore, a detailed investigation is required on the geographical distribution and habitat utilisation patterns, feeding ecology, and impact of herbivores on important plant populations [4]. The researcher also assesses the efficiency of farmers in enhancing their livelihood through tussar sericulture in the Bastar district [5]. The researchers framed a structured questionnaire to get an unbiased opinion from artisans regarding their working conditions and various steps required for better productivity. The main hurdles found in the survey are quality and quantity production, the supply of quality cocoons for reeling, continuous electricity supply during weaving, proper wage structure for the artisan, and the need for improved machinery [6]. The tussar silk has the potential to provide employment and also raise income levels in the rural sector in Jharkhand. The researcher found that knowledge of technology positively impacts the productivity of tussar silk fabric so that the tussar silk garment Industry grows and benefits its stakeholders [7].

2. The common crafts of Jharkhand

Bamboo and cane are the most commonly used by the villagers of Jharkhand in their daily lives, as they are lightweight and easy to carry. Bamboo has inherent antibacterial properties, which makes it excellent for food storage. The ornaments worn by the tribals are made of bell metal, brass, bamboo, or terracotta. *Sohrai* and *Khovar* paintings, tussar silk weaving, wood carving, sabai grass crafts, and dokra metal crafts are some important crafts in Jharkhand.

3. Kuchai silk

A small village, '*Kuchai*', in the Kharsawan Block of the Seraikela-Kharsawan District, is well-known for cultivating silkworms and making silk sarees. This wild silk spreads all over the Seraikela-Kharsawan District of Jharkhand. *Kuchai* silk, also known as 'Tussar silk,' unfolds a timeless facet of cultural legacy among indigenous communities, primarily in the *Santhal Parganas* district.

The silkworms grow on Sal, Arjun, and Asan trees. The disease in the caterpillar spread during the larvae stage before forming a cocoon, and the caterpillar died. This was the worst period for the farmers and weavers, especially the ones who had taken on loan debt. *Pebrine* is the most common disease in caterpillars, spreading rapidly among silkworms if not controlled on time. *Pebrine* is caused by a microsporidian parasite known as '*Nosema bombycis*' that affects the silkworm's digestive system, leading to discolouration and preventing them from growing. Figure 1 shows a dead caterpillar due to this disease. Bacterial diseases are mainly caused by the '*Flacherie*' virus and predominantly occur in the rainy season. In mycosis, the larva becomes rigid and inactive about 12 h after infection. These diseases cause total crop failure; if the mother is infected, her eggs will also carry that infection. To get disease-free laying, proper hygiene in the field and the grainage room needs to be maintained, and the disinfection of worms and feeding the larvae with healthy nutrition leaves are provided. The production of *Kuchai* silk revived after 2000 with more scientific processes and people adopted the scientific method, leaving behind the traditional process so that the caterpillars are disease-free.

Figure 1: Dead caterpillar due to pebrine disease

4. Tussar (*Antheraea mylitta*) silkworm

Jharkhand produces three types of silk i.e., mulberry, eri, and tussar. Jharkhand is mainly renowned for tussar silk production and the villagers who do sericulture in the Seraikela Kharsawan district produce tussar silk, known as 'Kosa silk or Vanya silk'. *Antheraea mylitta*, the Indian tussar silkworm, is widely spread across tropical regions of the country due to its insect species *polyphagia*, resulting in extensive population variation.

Almost nineteen eco-races, depending upon the geo-ecological conditions, have been found in *Antheraea mylitta*. They primarily feed on '*Terminalia*' species (Arjun tree) and '*Shorea robusta*' (Sal tree) but also have other secondary food plants. The dominant eco-race, which is spread all over *Kuchai* and the district, is bivoltine DABA that has two life cycles or generations per year reared in the forest on arjuna and *asan*, usually results in higher-quality silk than a uni-voltine (single-generation) silkworms [8]. Figures 2 and 3 show *Antheraea mylitta* and tussar moth.

Figure 2: *Antheraea mylitta* Figure 3: Tussar moths

4.1 Pre-cocoon activities

Figure 4: illustrates the life cycle of silkworms

4.1.1 Tree for sericulture

- Indian Laurel (*Terminalia Tomentosa*)

Generic name/ Local name: *Asan ka ped*

Indian laurel (Figure 5a) produces wide-spreading leaves. It's a primary source of food for caterpillars and is easily available in tropical evergreen forests.

- Arjuna Tree (*Terminalia arjuna*)

Generic name/Local name: *Arjun ka ped*

Terminalia arjuna (Figure 5b) leaves help silkworms grow by providing them with the required nutrition. Apart from this, *Terminalia arjuna* is a deciduous tree traditionally used as a medicine for pain.

Figure 5: a) Indian laurel and b) Terminalia arjuna

4.1.2 Equipment used for sericulture

Earthen pot

It is locally called *Matka* and is made of clay which is baked at a high temperature to make it hard. It is used for keeping the moths to lay their eggs.

Hygrometer

It is used to measure humidity or moisture and monitor the grainage room temperature and humidity for the eggs of the moth and the cocoon.

Microscope

It is used to detect the disease of moths or caterpillars. If any moth or caterpillar is infected, it is buried immediately to avoid spreading the disease.

Dyprotex

It is locally called *Dawai* and acts as a steriliser to protect it from contaminants or bodily fluids. It is used to disinfect the eggs of the moth.

Sickle

Locally it is called *Hasua*. It's a tool which has a sharp curved metal blade to cut grass and is used to cut the stem and detach the cocoon from the stem.

Jute rope

Jute rope is easy to splice, and handle, and is very durable. It is used to form garlands of cocoons where cocoons are loosely tied with the jute rope. Figure 6 shows equipment used during sericulture.

Figure 6: Various equipment used in sericulture

4.2 Pre-cocoon process

Stage 1: Egg

An egg laid by the female moth is the first stage of the silkworm's life cycle. A female moth can lay up to 150 to 300 eggs. Each moth is separated into a 'cylinder earthen pot' or '*matka*'. They lay the eggs entirely in 2 to 3 days in cool and humid conditions where a temperature of 28°C to 30°C is maintained using a hygrometer. After laying eggs, each female moth is checked under the microscope to see if they are infected with any disease; if infected, they are removed immediately along with the eggs and buried so they do not infect others. The trained villagers can quickly detect any disease in the caterpillar. After a proper examination, the DFLs (disease-free laying) or eggs are washed and disinfected with a Dyprotex sterilizer to remove any remaining infection. In the traditional method,

villagers used turmeric to disinfect the eggs. The eggs are dipped in the turmeric solution for 10 to 15 minutes and dried under the shed.

Stage 2: Silkworms

It's the most critical time for the farmers; the eggs are hatched, and now a dull brownish-yellow caterpillar with its black head peak from the egg is ready to meet a new world. The hatched larvae change their colour from dull brownish yellow to green and black head into brown within the day. For the next few days, their mission is to eat and increase by 12 times in size. In the larvae stage, they undergo the most painful process of shedding their skin. In their five-instar larval period, they moult four times in 30 to 35 days. The farmers feed the caterpillars on Arjun and Asan trees and take care of them so they are not out of food. The tree height would be 10 ft to 14 ft, which would be easy for farmers to handle. In a few days, caterpillars will eat all the leaves and the farmer has to transfer them from one tree to another.

Another thing that farmers have to take care of is predators. They have to take care of the birds and insects. Some villagers use the net to take care of them. To keep the caterpillar free from disease, farmers take some prophylactic measures in the rearing field using a disinfectant on the caterpillar, as shown in Figure 7, so the caterpillar is disease-free.

Figure 7: Applying disinfectant on the caterpillar

Stage 3: Pupa

In the final moult stage, the caterpillar stops eating and secretes a filament of fine, protein-rich saliva for 8 to 10 days without a break. They spin cocoons around them. The caterpillar rotates around 300,000 times to create a durable, beautiful, and robust habitat. The female caterpillar spins a bigger cocoon than the male silkworm. They use the two salivary glands on their heads to produce a protein gum called sericin. Sericin binds the silk threads together, which gives protection until it turns into a brown pupa (Figure 8a).

To attach the cocoon to the stem, the stalk is made by the silkworm, which is very strong and securely attached to the stem. Once the cocoon (Figure 8b) is formed, the silk thread is almost 1 km long within 40 days, the caterpillar retires from the buzzing forest, and it's time to take a long nap. During metamorphosis, nearly 15 to 20 days are taken for the change from pupa to adult moth. A week later, the cocoon becomes hard and compact. The farmers remove it by cutting the stem without damaging the stalk with *Hasua* (sickle) (Figure 8c). The colour of the cocoon, like grey, white or golden yellow, depends upon what the caterpillar has eaten.

**Figure 8: a) pupa, b) cocoon, c) women cutting stems of eaten leaves
d) garland of cocoons, e) cocoons are hung in drainage room**

Stage 4: Moth

Lumang, *lugum*, *goti*, and *koyi* are some local names for cocoons used by the 'Santhalis' and other tribal communities in the village. After detaching the cocoons from their host plant, they are ready to form a garland of cocoons loosely tied with a *rassi* or rope (Figure 8d) and hung in the grainage room (Figure 8e). Each garland has

100 cocoons, and each grainage house contains one lakh cocoons. The grainage house size is made with proper planning. The exact temperature is maintained up to 28°C to 30°C. Depending upon the temperature, humidity, and environmental conditions, the moth will come out of the cocoon, usually after 20 to 30 days. In a few days, the pupa changes into an adult moth, and the adult moth will pierce one end of the cocoon and emerge.

The adult moths (male and female) will perform the most important task in their life cycle: they begin to mate, mostly at night, and the process is called ‘coupling’. The female moth is dull yellow, and the male moths are brown. They have characteristic mirror-like circles on their wings. The female moth mates once in a lifetime, and the male will mate more than twice, but soon after, he dies. The following day, after mating, the moth has to decouple; the female's wings are clipped to prevent disease transmission and to ensure that the eggs remain uncontaminated during collection. The female moth lays eggs, and once again, the life cycle of the silkworm begins. The grainage room for the fertility of egg and moth is shown in Figure 9.

The male *Antheraea mylitta* moth has prominently bushy and feathery antennae, which are highly sensitive and specialised for detecting pheromones emitted by females from long distances, aiding in successful mating. On the other hand, the female's antennae are less feathery and comparatively finer, as their primary role is not to seek mates but to lay eggs.

Figure 9: Grainage room for the fertility of a) eggs and b) moth

4.3 Post-cocoon activities

4.3.1 Stifling

For high-quality silk without fibre breakage, it is necessary to kill the pupa, which has not yet come out of the cocoon. The process of stifling is used, through which pupa in the cocoon is killed by applying hot air or steaming for 10 to 15 min. This will also preserve the silk for a long period. The villagers eat the dead pupa left out after reeling, a good source of protein, minerals, and vitamins. It is also used in medicine and healthcare products for humans and animals.

4.3.2 Cooking

Cocoon cooking is a process of removing the sericin to make it soft by penetration of hot water outside to inside of the cocoon and vice-versa. This will help unwind the continuous filament without breakage. For cooking, 100 cocoons of similar sizes and hardness are selected. In a cooker, ‘eenta,’ i.e. brick is placed inside a cooker as a base so the cocoons are not burned. For 100 cocoons 1.5 litre of water, 10 ml of H₂O₂ and 10 g of sunlight soap are needed. Hydrogen peroxide and sunlight soap remove a small quantity of sericin and provide a better spinning and elongation of the silk, making it easier to reel. When the water is boiling, the cocoons are packed in plastic bags and dipped in water. After half an hour, the plastic is turned to the opposite side and covered with the plate. On top of the plate, the brick is placed so that proper steaming and boiling of the cocoon is done.

4.3.3 Deflossing

There are three layers in the cocoon i.e., outer (cocoon coat), middle (cocoon layer), and inner (cocoon lining). The outermost layer is rough and has a coarser surface because sericin is present in large amounts. On the other hand, the inner layer of the cocoon contains finer silk; that is why the outer layer of envelopes of silkworm cocoons is removed. Therefore, removing the outermost layer of the cocoon's rough and loose envelopes is called deflossing; this increases the silk's quality and price. In the village, it is hand-operated by the women. 5 to 6 women sit together and defloss the cocoon using a brush with care so that the inner layer is not damaged. Figure 10 shows the deflossing process of the cooked cocoon by a villager.

Figure 10: a) Cooked cocoon, b) Deflossing of cooked cocoon

4.4 Traditional method of reeling

Before adopting the scientific method and instrument, villagers of *Kuchai*, Seraikela Kharsawan district used different methods for reeling silk, i.e. unwinding the silk fibres from softened cocoons. Traditionally, the wild tussar is divided into many sub-categories, two of which are *Ghicha* and *Katia* silk. They are both made of damaged, leftover, cut, or pierced cocoons, preventing the natural reeling of the silk. It promotes sustainability in the textile industry. *Gicha* and *Katia* silk is spun yarn, which is reeled manually by the women of the village.

Ghicha silk

Ghicha is derived from the word ‘*ghichha*’, which means ‘waste’. The origin of tussar *ghicha* silk can be traced back to the Jharkhand tribal communities. It is also produced in Bihar by Bhagalpur and Chhattisgarh weavers. It does not require a regular process of reeling. *Gicha* silk sarees are lightweight, breathable, and softer than *Katia* silk, as the minimal twist is given; during weaving, threads can be untwisted in a localised area. This gives softness to the fabric with a beautiful texture and earthy feel and makes it ideal for warm weather. Tribal women are practised enough in weaving *Ghicha* silk and can produce plain silk saree in 3 days.

Ghicha silk yarns are a by-product of the tussar silk production process and are often spun by hand. It is generally coarser and less shiny compared to *Katia* silk. It has an uneven and slubby textured and somewhat rustic feel with a matte finish. The fabric tends to be thicker and stronger, making it more durable and mainly used for traditional wear like sarees, stoles, etc.

However, these days, there is minimal production of *ghicha* silk in the *Kuchai* Kharsawan District because of less funding and support from the government. Figure 11 and Figure 12 depict illustrations of reeling *ghicha* silk.

Figure 11: Illustration of reeling of *ghicha* silk

Figure 12: Traditional method of reeling *ghicha* silk yarn

Katia silk

‘*Katia* silk’ is also called ‘*tar* silk,’ and it is made from ‘*phuki*’ or pierced cocoon. *Katia* is a unique handwoven made from wild tussar silk, which is soft and thick with distinctive textures. It is spun with short tussar silk waste filaments. The name ‘*tar*’ was given because of its thick and strong yarn formation after twisting the fibres. *Katia*

silk saree is known for its durability and good abrasion resistance without losing its lustre. Figure 13 shows the reeling process of *Katia* silk and *Katia* silk yarn.

Katia silk is more uniform and known for its lustrous shine and smooth texture. It has a softer and lighter feel compared to *Ghicha* silk and is mainly used for producing formal wear, sarees, and dupattas.

Figure 13: a) Reeling of *Katia* silk, b) *Katia* silk yarn

Reeled silk

Reeling is a process of getting fine silk yarn from the cocoons, much finer than spun yarn. The yarn produced by this process is called reeled silk. It is a high-quality silk reeled with continuous filament from the different cocoons into a yarn. It is rich in lustre, smooth and bright. After 2006, when an organisation called Jharcraft was set up in Jharkhand, they trained villagers to produce a reeled yarn using a reeling-cum-twisting-machine (Figure 14b) developed by CSTRI Bangalore, but this needed water at 40°C to 45°C, which required a boiler. Then, in 2011, Jharcraft developed its solar-powered reeling machine, ‘*Samriddhi*’. Several solar panels are placed on the terrace where the reeling machine is operated. This semi-automatic machine is 5 to 6 times more effective than a manual and reduces labour. Figure 15 shows the cocoon and reeled yarn produced as depicted in Figure 14.

Figure 14: a) Solar panels, b) Reeling-cum-twisting-machine, c) Reeled yarn making, d) Re-reeling machine

Figure 15: a) Cocoons, b) reeled yarn

4.5 Weaving

The exact origin of weaving is difficult to trace in Jharkhand. However, the basic principles of weaving were used to make baskets or fences by interlacing twigs and branches during Neolithic times. From ancient times, handloom weaving has played an important role in shaping the economies and culture of Jharkhand and is passed down from generation to generation. The weaving of *Kuchai* silk is done in a normal treadle loom. Converting yarn into fabric has to go through several phases: winding, creeling, warping, drawing-in, and weaving.

4.5.1 Winding (*Suta ghumetna*)

The transfer of the hank into the bobbin is called winding. A spinning wheel machine carries out this process. The hank is placed on a stand, and the bobbin is placed on the spindle blade. With one hand, the paddle is operated, and with the other hand, tension is given to the yarn for winding. Figure 16 illustrates the winding operation of a spinning wheel.

Figure 16: Illustration of winding using a spinning wheel machine

4.5.2 Creeling and warping

Creeling and warping are performed together. The weavers of *Kuchai* silk perform sectional warping because all the threads are arranged uniformly in less time. In sectional warping, the yarns that are passed through the reed during creeling will be placed on a wooden drum and then the drum is rotated, this will organize the yarns into several bands. Then, the yarn sheet will be transferred to the weaver's beam and the process is called warping.

Figure 17: Illustration of creeling and warping of yarn

4.5.3 Drawing-in

This process comes after the sheet of yarn is placed on a weaver's beam. Drawing-in consists of two processes: drafting and denting.

4.5.4 Drafting

The order of passing the warp thread through the heald of the heald shaft in a particular order is called drafting. In the *Kuchai* silk saree, weavers do a plain weave, which requires two heald shafts (Figure 18a). The single thread is passed through each heald eye of a shaft with the help of a hook.

4.5.5 Denting

Drawing the warp thread to the dent of the reed is known as denting. They use 100s and 120s reeds to make silk fabric.

After the loom is set, weavers are ready to weave, and the operation of handloom is easy to understand. With daily practice, weavers of *Kuchai* form a rhythm of pressing a treadle, throwing a shuttle (Figure 18b), etc. Weavers can weave eight meters of silk saree in three days of hard work and dedication. The extra weft is also used to make geometric or small designs using an extra shuttle inserted manually. The silk saree formed is not just a piece of cloth; it is the conscientiousness and commitment of all the villagers who produced raw material from sericulture to form a cloth.

Figure 18: a) Two heald shafts for plain weave, b) Shuttle

5. Coloration

After weaving, the silk fabric is boiled with soap and water to remove the gum or sericin from the fabric. This process is also called 'dhulaye' or 'degumming'. However, after *dhulaye*, the fabric is sent for surface embellishment or to the dyeing sector, where dyeing, printing, and finishing are done. In Seraikela Kharsawan, the fabrics are sent to the village women for embroidery. The craftsmen of that place only process raw silk fabric. However, silk fabric is sent to Ranchi or Hazaribagh for the dyeing process, where natural and synthetic dyes are used for manufacturing products. Earlier, only natural dyes were the source of dyeing. However, at present people are trained to use synthetic and natural dyes with mordents. A different pattern of the block is carved by artisans and supplied to the block printing sector, where women in the village print the fabric according to the design. In the end, to improve the appearance and feel of the cloth, they apply textile finishing to *Kuchai* silk fabrics.

6. Motifs

Traditionally, stripes and geometric shapes were used in dresses. But to stand within the competition in the market, people started decorating the fabric with different motifs inspired by leaves, flowers, birds and human figures. Figure 19 shows some motifs on the final fabrics.

Figure 19: a) Tribal motifs, b) Floral motifs, c) Block printing with geometric patterns

7. Embroidery

Different embroidery is used to decorate the saree such as the 'Santha' embroidery of Jharkhand which visualises various phases of the *Santhal* lifestyle other than the 'Kantha' stitch of West Bengal, 'Chikankari' of Uttar Pradesh and 'Zardozi'. Women of villagers decorate the fabrics with vibrant colour threads and intricate designs using stitches like satin and chain (Figure 20).

Figure 20: Embroidery on silk sarees

8. Specification and Pricing

Table 1 shows the price of the final products along with the material used.

Table 1: Product specification and pricing

Product (Local name)	Usual size	Fabric used	Price (₹)
<i>Kuchai</i> Silk Saree	8 m	Silk, Silk-Cotton	6,000 - 15,000
Tassar Running fabric	1 m	Silk	700 - 5,000
Ladies Kurti	L: 45 in, W: 20in	Silk, Silk-Cotton	900 - 1,500
Men's Shirt	L:30 in, W:21in	Silk, Silk-Cotton	900 - 1,500
Men's Kurta	L: 40in, W: 23 in	Silk, Silk-Cotton	700 - 1,500
Men's Bandis	L: 28in: W: 21in	Silk, Silk-Cotton, Silk-Viscose	1,000 - 3,000

9. Marketing Channels

In Jharkhand, the local bazaars, such as Ranchi Market, Jamshedpur, Dhanbad, and smaller towns, are important spaces where traditional textiles like *Kuchai* silk are marketed. These markets attract both residents and tourists. Participating in local craft fairs or exhibitions in Jharkhand (like the Jharkhand State Handicraft & Handloom Exhibition) allows artisans to showcase *Kuchai* silk products. These events help build awareness and attract buyers interested in authentic handcrafted textiles. The flowchart of the movement of silk production in Jharkhand is described in Figure 21.

Retail

Jharcraft has showrooms in Jharkhand, Bihar, New Delhi, Ahmedabad, Bangalore, and Mumbai, selling *Kuchai* silk products.

Export

The state's organic silk is in high demand in the USA, Sweden, the UK, Germany, London, Turkey, Brazil, China, Cambodia, and Lithuania. These are the major importers associated with Jharcraft.

Urban and rural haats

The concept of '*Haat*' is unique to itself as it is established based on the nation's ancient culture. It is a 'Bazar' or '*Haat*' where various business merchants sell the products on particular weekdays. Large areas are marked, and small huts are made in Jharkhand to sell the products. The urban '*Haat*' mainly takes place in Hazaribagh and Mysore. In contrast, the rural haats are in the nearby village areas. This supports the artisans in living a settled life by providing them with a livelihood.

Figure 21: Flowchart of the movement of silk production in Jharkhand

10. Conclusion

Kuchai silk, an ancient tradition of Jharkhand, is a livelihood in rural areas, produced by tussar silkworms on Asan and Arjun trees, starting in Seraikela-Kharsawan. Presently to sustain in the competitive market, apart from sarees, the artisans in the Seraikela region produce products like kurtis, skirts, shirts, and many other dresses. With the help of government and non-profit organisations, *Kuchai* silk has gained its name nationally and internationally. The growth in the economy of Jharkhand as the demand for *Kuchai* silk has increased in recent years (Figure 22). Apart from Seraikela-Kharsawan, different regions of Jharkhand, like Ranchi, Dumka, Godda, and Hazaribagh, are the primary producers of *Kuchai* silk.

Many people in *Kuchai* silk production have another source of income, i.e. agriculture, to fulfil their daily needs (Figure 23). Not all craftsmen are into this craft; men are involved in other work in different sectors, and women work in training centres from 11 am to 4 pm or in their respective homes. Women of the village feel independent and proud to earn for their families. Although silk production has allowed women weavers to be satisfied, they need to get a better amount for their hard work and dedication that they deserve for making fabric due to business-to-business transactions. Middlemen buy the products at meagre cost and sell them at very high prices.

Figure 22: Growth of Kuchai silk

Figure 23: Source of income

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